

Тезисы
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АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВЫЗОВЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ

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Переяслав

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Қорытынды.

Емдеу 7 күн қамтылды. Кестедегі емдеу шарасы шаруашылық үшін тиімді болып табылады. Сыйрлар №1 кесте бойынша 11-12 емдеу күндері жазылды. №2 кесте бойынша емделген сыйрлар 10-14 емдеу күндері жазылды. №3 кесте бойынша емдеу жүргізілген сыйрлар 8-10 емдеу күндері жазылды. Сонымен осы 3 кестедегі көрсетілген емдеу схемалының ішінен тиімдісі 3 кесте бойынша емдеу жүргізу болып табылды.

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IMMUNOMICROBIOLOGICAL CONDITION OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN SCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE CITY OF BUKHARA

Abstract – a special place among dental diseases is occupied by diseases of the mucous membrane (CO) of the oral cavity (PR) (SOPR). Recently, there has been an increase in the number of inflammatory diseases of SOPR. This is due both to an increase in the number of adverse factors affecting the body, and to a decrease in the standard of living of the population. The severity and prevalence of SOPR diseases is determined by the nature of the etiological factor and the intensity of aggression [1, 2, 3, 4, 5].

Key words – etiological factor, dental diseases, inflammatory diseases, immunomicrobiological, bacteriological laboratory.

I. Introduction

To determine the importance of the immunomicrobiological state of PR as risk factors for the formation and development of diseases of SOPR in children in a hot climate.

Materials and methods of research: In 210 healthy and 81 patients, aged from 12 to 18 years old, children with SOPR diseases conducted microbiological studies in the traditional style; sampling of biological material and its delivery to the bacteriological laboratory according to the methods of M.N. Zubkov, 2004, sowing of biological material (oral liquid) was carried out according to Gold, identification was carried out according to Bergy's Manual Systematic Bacteriology (1997); To study antimicrobial resistance, the disk diffusion method was used (Kh.I. Iskhakova et al. 2015) and the results were interpreted according to MUK 4.2.1890-04. At the same time, we determined the concentration of immunoglobulins of the main three classes of IgA, IgG, IgM in the blood serum of healthy and sick children involved in the examination, carried out by the conventional method of radial immunodiffusion according to Mancini (1964); determination of the level of total IgE was carried out in blood serum by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA); sIgA content was determined by ELISA by conventional methods; determination of lysozyme in saliva was carried out using the methods proposed by Kagramanova K.A. and Ermolieva Z.V. (1966); the level of lactoferrin was determined on a two-site solid-phase ELISA using a test system and determining the cellular composition of the gums according to the method of Leonov L.E. et al. (2002). The results obtained were processed by generally accepted statistical methods for biomedical research according to Student and Fisher.

II. Analysis

Microbiological studies showed that in the examined healthy children of older school age, not only representatives of the normal microflora of PR were sown, but also of conditionally pathogenic microflora (UPM): It was found that children of 12-14 and 15-18 age groups were more often not seeded representatives of the Streptococcus genus - in 87 out of 105 (82.9%) children 12-14 years old and 71 out of 105 (67.6%) children 15-18 years old. In the following places were Veilonella spp (respectively in 72.4% and 68.6%), non-pathogenic Neisseria spp (respectively in 35.2% and 30.5%), Actinomices spp (respectively in 35, 2% and 30.5%).

According to the study of the seeding of microorganism strains from the PR of the examined children, Lactobacillus spp (0.2% and 2.6%, 13.0 times difference), non-pathogenic Neisseria spp (respectively 0.9% and 6.9%, the difference is 7.7 times), Actinomices spp (respectively 1.4% and 6.4%, the difference is 4.6 times), non-pathogenic Streptococcus spp (respectively 3.4% and 14.4%, the difference is 4.2 times), Veilonella spp (respectively 4.1% and 12.6%, the difference is 3.1 times), Candida spp (respectively 2.4% and 4, 8%, a difference of 2.0 times) and others.

However, it must be emphasized that the strains of UPM practically did not differ from each other; So, Enterococcus spp (respectively in 1.4% and 2.0%), E.coli (respectively in 2.3% and 2.7%) and other genera of the Enterobacteriaceae family (respectively in 1, 4% and 1.6%) were sown almost at the same level. But, pathogenic microorganisms such as S.aureus were more often sown as a monoculture - respectively 2.9% and 1.1% (a difference of 2.6 times).

Table 1.
**Comparative Parameters of the Microbial Landscape of the Oral Cavity
in Healthy and Patients with SOPR of Older School Children**

Pathogens	Healthy children n = 210		SOPR diseases n = 81	
	Abs	%	Abs	%
Streptococcus spp (not pathogenic)	158	75,2	49	60,5
S.epidermidis	55	26,2	37	45,7
S.aureus	36	17,1	32	39,5
S.saprophyticus	25	11,9	9	11,1
Neisseria spp (not pathogenic)	69	32,9	12	14,8
Enterococcus spp	30	14,3	19	23,5
Veilonella spp	148	70,5	64	79,0
E.coli	44	21,0	28	34,6
Др. роды семе-ва Enterobacteriaceae	26	12,4	23	28,4
Pseudomonas spp	48	22,9	28	34,6
Bacteroides spp	25	11,9	12	14,8
Peptostreptococcus spp	65	31,0	31	38,3
Candida spp	64	30,5	45	55,6
Actinomyces spp	69	32,9	32	39,5
Lactobacillus spp	25	11,9	12	14,8
Total seeded strains	887		433	

This concerns the inoculation of non-pathogenic *Streptococcus* spp (75.2% and 60.5%, respectively), non-pathogenic *Neisseria* spp (32.9% and 14.8%, respectively). But the sowing rate of UPM and PM was significantly greater in sick children with SOPR diseases.

When studying the factors of non-specific protection of PR in children of senior school age; it was found that the percentage of lymphocytes among both age groups showed practically no significant differences - $1.3 \pm 0.1\%$ and $1.4 \pm 0.1\%$, respectively ($P > 0.05$). According to the content of monocytes, various forms of neutrophils, there were also no significant differences between these age groups of children ($P > 0.05$). The results show that the parameters of lymphocytes and monocytes in children with SOPR diseases were significantly reduced in relation to the data of healthy children - $1.0 \pm 0.1\%$ and $1.3 \pm 0.1\%$, respectively; $2.0 \pm 0.1\%$ and $2.7 \pm 0.1\%$ ($P < 0.05$): The parameters of stab neutrophils, on the contrary, were increased in sick children with SOP compared with healthy children - $3.8 \pm 0, 4\%$ and $2.9 \pm 0.4\%$.

The results on the content of PR immunoglobulins show IgA detected 1.1 times significantly more in children 15-18 years old compared with data for children 12-14 years old - 1.51 ± 0.16 g / l and 1.43 ± 0 , respectively 12 g / l ($P < 0.05$); almost the same trend in IgM level (respectively 1.30 ± 0.14 g / l and 1.21 ± 0.10 g / l, the difference is 1.1 times, $P < 0.05$) and IgG (respectively, 15.92 ± 0.74 g / l and 14.79 ± 0.46 g / l, the difference is 1.1 times, $P < 0.05$). The content of sIgA was 1.1 times higher in healthy children 15-18 years old compared with healthy children 12-14 years old - 4.87 ± 0.42 g / l and 4.58 ± 0.27 g, respectively/l Although the indicators do not significantly differ from each other ($P > 0.05$), the data are noteworthy.

A study of factors of nonspecific resistance in healthy and sick children with SOPR diseases revealed that the content of IgA, IgM, IgG in PR in sick children with SOPR diseases changed in different directions; the content of IgA and IgM was reduced, respectively, 1.4 times (1.47 ± 0.14 g / l versus 1.06 ± 0.07 g / l, $P < 0.05$) and 1.3 times (1.26 ± 0.12 g / l versus 0.98 ± 0.06 g / l, $P < 0.05$), then the IgG content was increased by 1.3 times in sick children in relation to the data of healthy children (15.36 ± 0.60 versus 19.34 ± 0.72 , $P < 0.05$).

Practically the same tendency of changes concerned the contents of lysozyme and lactoferrin in the oral fluid of the examined healthy and sick children in a comparative analysis; healthy ones averaged 4.51 ± 0.57 μ g / l, then the parameters with SOPR diseases were 1.4 times significantly less - on average 3.15 ± 0.28 μ g / l ($P < 0.05$); and lactoferrin (respectively 1986.26 ± 27.63 ng / ml versus 1065.89 ± 19.25 ng / ml, $P < 0.001$), with the only difference (a decrease of 1.9 times). A comparative study of the content of local immunity factors found that in sick children of advanced school age with SOPR diseases these indicators change in different directions, if IgG is increased in patients, then IgA and IgM were reduced in relation to the parameters of their healthy peers.

Thus established; firstly, representatives of NM PR were sown relatively more in healthy children 12-14 years old, in relation to healthy children 15-18 years old; secondly, UPM strains were sown more in healthy children 15-18 years old compared to children 12-14 years old; thirdly, practically identical results were obtained from the biological material of anaerobes; fourthly, fungi of the genus *Candida* are relatively more found from PR in children 12-14 years old, compared with the age group 15-18 years old; the microbial landscape of PR in children of high school age, depending on the number of strains, was more often sown as an association of microorganisms, and pathogenic strains were more often identified as a monoculture of strains.

III. Conclusion

Comparative parameters of factors of nonspecific resistance of oral fluid in healthy older children showed that the content of IgG, IgA, IgM, sIgA, lysozyme and lactoferrin did not reveal inter-age differences between healthy older children; When comparing local immunity factors, it was found that in patients of senior school age children with SOPR diseases these indicators change in different directions, if IgG is increased in patients, then IgA and IgM were reduced in relation to the parameters of their healthy peers.

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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ БАКТЕРИОФАГОВ В ПРОФИЛАКТИКЕ ВОСПАЛИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ПОЛОСТИ РТА ПРИ РЕВМАТИЗМА

Основным средством для лечения воспалительных заболеваний пародонта, согласно рекомендациям Стоматологической Ассоциации Узбекистана, являются антисептические средства. Кроме них, при необходимости, рекомендуется использование противомикробных средств. (1) Но так, как эти средства не обладают избирательностью действия, они подавляют и облигатную микрофлору, вместе с её полезными свойствами (стимуляция развития лимфоидной ткани, антагонистическое 100 воздействие на патогенную микрофлору, поддержание физиологического воспаления и готовности к иммунным реакциям, и пр.)(1, 2) Так же пародонтологи все чаще отмечают рост числа пациентов с лекарственной непереносимостью, развитие таких побочных эффектов и осложнений противомикробной терапии, как аллергические и дисбиотические изменения в полости рта(3). Кроме того, противомикробные препараты могут приводить к развитию устойчивых штаммов микроорганизмов. Исходя из этого, многие авторы говорят о кризисе антибактериальной терапии.

Цель исследования. Благодаря вышеперечисленным факторам, активно идет поиск альтернативных методик лечения, таких, как использование пробиотиков, в качестве антагонистов парадонтопатогенов. Во многих отраслях медицины, в том числе и в стоматологии, успешно применяются бактериофаги. В своей работе мы пытаемся определить эффективность препаратов на основе бактериофагов в сочетании с пробиотическими средствами в отношении лечения воспалительных заболеваний полости рта. С этой целью, на первом этапе исследования, нами был выбран и проверен на работоспособность препарат

«Фагодент» (Микромир), как основной кандидат на роль бактериофагального препарата. В отличие от других препаратов, содержащих бактериофаги, «Фагодент» разработан специально для борьбы с патогенной микрофлорой полости рта, в состав этого препарата включены бактериофаги, тропные к следующим возбудителям: *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*, *Actinomyces israelii*, *Actinomyces* spp., *Bacteroides gracilis*, *Bacteroides forsythus*, *Campylobacter* spp., *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Fusobacterium* spp., *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Prevotella intermedia*, *Proteus vulgaris* spp., *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*